

ABSTRACTS

1. Chemioterapia. 1986 Feb;5(1):58-60.

Development of laboratory hormone tests and their application in the monitoring of cancer patients.

Mondina R, Pirondini A, Baroni M, Borsellino G, Mondina L, Poma S, Secchi GC, Polvani F.

In the endocrinologic study of dysplastic and neoplastic pathologies of hormone-dependent organs we propose the determination not only of the plasma levels of the "total" hormone but also those of the free hormone as well as the plasma/hormone binding capacity and the kinetics of the plasma/steroid interaction.

PMID: 3955785 [PubMed - indexed for MEDLINE]

2. Chemioterapia. 1986 Jun;5(3):154-8.

Current status of hormone receptor measurements in cancer patients.

Pirondini A, Baroni M, Borsellino G, Marchesi P, Mondina L, Mondina R, Poma S, Sonato A, Secchi GC, Polvani F.

Despite increasingly sophisticated techniques, improvements in the correlation between laboratory findings and tumor response to endocrine therapy have not been obtained by hormone receptor studies. A possible explanation is that present knowledge of the mechanisms of the endocrine stimulus is incomplete. Some aspects of the present model, (elevated conjugated steroid levels, multiplicity of the plasma proteins capable of binding hormones, pulsatility of the plasma protein bond and of the receptor system for steroids), are still unclear and thus are not used in diagnosis. By evaluating these factors it will probably be possible to correlate better laboratory data with clinical findings.

PMID: 3013433 [PubMed - indexed for MEDLINE]

3. Cancer. 1989 Jan 15;63(2):305-8.

Breast carcinoma and plasma 17β -estradiol binding.

Mondina R, Borsellino G, Pirondini A, Polvani F, Baroni M, Secchi G, Poma S, Pellegrini G.

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The data relating to plasma steroid binding and transport (usually measured with dehydrotestosterone) are controversial. The plasma E2 binding of 79 breast carcinoma patients, 19 premenopausal and 60 postmenopausal, were compared to 46 controls, 21 premenopausal and 25 postmenopausal. In this study the authors removed the endogenous steroids with charcoal, incubated the plasma with

17-beta-E2 in non-saturation conditions, and used ammonium sulfate to precipitate the complex. The authors chose 17-beta-E2 as ligand because the plasma steroid binding system has not been shown to be homogeneous and because this binding function may vary independently for the different steroids. In these patients, the E2 binding was significantly (P less than 0.01) increased (85 +/- 11 pg/ml and 73 +/- 13 pg/ml in premenopausal and postmenopausal) compared to the normal controls (59 +/- 7 pg/ml and 58 +/- 5 pg/ml in premenopausal and postmenopausal women. It is still unclear whether this is a primary increase of the binding capacity or a reaction of the host for sequestering excess circulating E2. However, the small percentage of false-positives and false-negatives suggests

4. Ann Ostet Ginecol Med Perinat. 1989 Nov-Dec;110(6):283-9.9.

[Prognosis factors in epithelial tumors of the ovary]

[Article in Italian]

Fattori di prognosi nei tumori epiteliali dell'ovaio

L.Frigerio L. Busci, A. Pirondini, S. Garsia, M. Caldarella, G. Pifarotti, A. Ferrari

Summary: 87 patients treated for epithelial ovarian carcinoma between 1975 and 1986 were evaluated intensively. In all cases the original operation was followed by surgical reassessment to evaluate the result of adjuvant therapy and to study the cases without apparent disease. The actuarial survival rate after 3 years, by Kaplan-Meier calculation, demonstrated 73.5% survival in patients with negative second-look versus 32% in presence of positive reassessment (P less than 0.01). Surgical reexploration and histologic study were negative in 34 cases (39%). Original stage, histotype, histological grading, peritoneal washing and age of patients were considered for prognostic evaluation of the tumor. The absence of residual tumor (RT) at first surgery resulted in complete response after adjuvant therapy in 70.8% of women, versus 25.8% with RT greater than 2 cm (P less than 0.01). Negative second-look appears the most important prognostic factor for the evaluation of epithelial ovarian cancer (P less than 0.001).

PMID: 2639615 [PubMed - indexed for MEDLINE]

Fra il 1975 e il 1976 sono state sottoposte a monitoraggio clinico intensivo 87 pazienti inizialmente trattate per una neoplasia epiteliale dell'ovaio. In tutti i casi considerati l'intervento laparotomico originario è stato seguito da una ristadiazione chirurgica per valutare gli effetti della terapia adiuvante instaurata e per controllare i casi apparentemente liberi da neoplasia. La sopravvivenza attuariale dopo tre anni, valutata attraverso il metodo di Kaplan e Meier, ha dimostrato una sopravvivenza del 73.5% quando la riesplorazione chirurgica è negativa rispetto al 32% in caso di chirurgia secondaria positiva ($p < 0.01$). L'esplorazione laparotomica e lo studio istologico eseguito durante l'intervento chirurgico secondario non hanno rilevato la persistenza della neoplasia in 34 casi (39%). Lo stadio originale della malattia, l'istotipo, il grading istologico, il lavaggio peritoneale e l'età delle pazienti sono stati considerati nella valutazione prognostica di questi tumori. L'assenza di tumore alla fine della prima istanza chirurgica consente di ottenere risposte complete dopo terapia

adiuvante nel 70.8% delle pazienti, a differenza del 25.8% nei casi con tumore residuo superiore a 2 cm ($p < 0.01$). La negatività al tempo chirurgico secondario costituisce il fattore prognostico indiscutibilmente più importante ($p < 0.001$).

5. Gynecology and Urology, Second World Week of Professional Updating in Surgery. Monduzzi Ed. pag. 7-10. 1990.

Prognostic value of second-look laparotomy for epithelial ovarian carcinoma

L. Frigerio, S. Garsia, L. Busci, A. Pirondini, G. Pifarotti, A. Ferrari

Summary: Between 1975 and 1986, Second-Look Laparotomy (SLL) to evaluate disease status was performed in 87 patients originally presenting with epithelial ovarian carcinoma. Surgical and histologic assessment did not reveal persistent disease in 34 patients (39%). The 3-years survival, by Kaplan and Meier calculation, was 73.5% after negative SLL versus 32% after positive SLL ($p < 0.01$). Seventeen of the 24 patients declared free of disease after original surgery remained negative at SLL (70.8%), 7 cases out of 12 with disease less than 2 cm resulted negative at reexploration (58.3%), but only 8 of 31 patients with tumor greater than 2 cm were free of disease at the time of SLL (25.8%), ($p < 0.01$). Recurrent carcinoma was subsequently documented in 13 of 34 patients (38.2%) that were negative at SLL. Additional diagnostic effort will be carried out to increase our knowledge about this severe disease.

6. Italian Journal of Gynecology and Obstetrics. Vol. 2, pag. 19-24. 1990.

The second-look laparotomy for epithelial ovarian carcinoma

L. Frigerio, L. Busci, S. Garsia, A. Pirondini, A. Ferrari

Summary: Between 1975 and 1986, second look laparotomy (SLL) to evaluate disease status was performed in 87 patients originally presenting with epithelial ovarian carcinoma. Surgical and histologic assessment did not reveal persistent disease in 34 patients (39%). The 3-years survival, by Kaplan-Meier calculation, was 73.5% after negative SLL versus 32% after positive SLL ($p < 0.01$). Residual tumor (RT) was absent after original operation in 24 patients (35.8%), in 12 cases (17.9%) RT was less than 2 cm, and in 31 cases (46.2%) RT was more than 2 cm. Negative SLL is related to RT at primary surgery. The merit of reassessment surgery is the prognostic value of this procedure: the mortality at 3 years after primary surgery was 26.5% of cases with negative SLL and 68% after positive SLL ($p < 0.01$).

7. Atti LVII Congresso Nazionale della Società Italiana di Ostetricia e Ginecologia. pag. 313-314. 1990

Valutazione dei recettori per estrogeni e progesterone nel carcinoma endometriale: studio comparativo su tessuto tumorale e "normale"

L. Frigerio, A. Pirondini, L. Busci, S. Garsia, A. Ferrari.

Summary: La frazione libera degli ormoni steroidei (estrogeni e progesterone) si lega a specifici recettori proteici ubicati a livello intracellulare. Nel nostro studio abbiamo determinato (con metodo di adsorbimento del carbone-destano)

contemporaneamente su tessuto tumorale e su tessuto endometriale "normale" la concentrazione dei recettori estrogenici e progestinici dopo isterectomia per carcinoma endometriale. In 10 casi da noi analizzati le concentrazioni recettoriali estrogeniche sono risultate notevolmente superiori nel tessuto neoplastico rispetto all'endometrio "normale" ($p < 0.01$). Si è inoltre rilevata una correlazione fra elevato grading istologico in 2 casi (G4) e bassa concentrazione recettoriale (< 200 fmoli/mg di proteina). Al contrario si è verificata una corrispondenza tra basso grading istologico in 8 casi (G2-G3) ed alta concentrazione recettoriale. Il confronto fra concentrazione recettoriale e grading istologico potrebbe identificare con maggior sicurezza le pazienti con alto grado di maturità del tumore e livelli estrogenici più elevati da sottoporre a trattamento ormonale.

8. Proceedings of Second World Week of Professional Updating in Surgery and in Surgical and Oncological Disciplines of the University of Milan. Monduzzi Ed. Bologna Vol. IX: pag. 7-10, July 15-21 1990.

Prognostic value of second-look laparotomy for epithelial ovarian carcinoma.

L. Frigerio, S. Garsia, L. Busci, A. Pirondini, G. Pifarotti, A. Ferrari

Summary: The clinical indications of second look laparotomy (SLL) include: (1) restaging of the patients by gynecologic oncologists after previous inadequate assessment, (2) studying the effects of chemotherapy after traditional regimens or clinical research protocols and (3) evaluating the patients apparently free of disease after chemotherapy. Residual tumor (RT) at primary surgery seems to be very important. We observed an overall survival of 58.8% after 3 years in cases with $RT=0$ or < 2 cm as opposed to 34.1% of cases with $RT > 2$ cm ($p < 0.05$). The importance of an optimal debulking at primary operation is well documented.

9. Medico e paziente, anno XVI, n.5, pag. 76-79. 1990.

Trattamento dei tumori ovarici

L.Frigerio, A.Pirondini, L.Busci, S.Ferrari

Summary: Il tumore ovarico viene diagnosticato spesso tardivamente, quando si è già diffuso alle strutture pelviche e agli organi addominali (III stadio), compromettendo talora il giudizio di operabilità della paziente. Il 65% dei casi giunti alla nostra osservazione è costituito da tumori al III stadio e ciò comporta una possibile riduzione della prognosi di sopravvivenza. Non esistono oggi metodiche di screening valide per l'identificazione precoce di questa patologia. L'intervento chirurgico laparotomico costituisce il cardine diagnostico e terapeutico nell'affronto dei tumori ovarici. Nei tumori epiteliali dell'ovaio in stadio avanzato la chirurgia citoredutiva consente di migliorare la sopravvivenza delle pazienti. Quando il tumore residuo alla fine dell'intervento originario risulta assente o inferiore a 2 cm abbiamo riscontrato una sopravvivenza attuariale del 58.8% dopo 3 anni rispetto al 34,1% nei casi con tumore residuo superiore a 2 cm ($p < 0.05$). L'effetto terapeutico della chirurgia e della chemioterapia adiuvante può essere verificato attraverso l'impiego

sistematico del second look laparotomico. Il ruolo terapeutico del second look laparotomico non è oggi chiaramente documentato. Nella nostra esperienza, quando il second look laparotomico risulta negativo la sopravvivenza a 36 mesi è del 71.8% contro il 42.8% se viene reso negativo nel corso dello stesso intervento. Se alla fine del second look il tumore residuo è inferiore a 2 cm la sopravvivenza a 36 mesi è del 26.6% contro una sopravvivenza nulla a 12 mesi se il tumore residuo è superiore a 2 cm. Attualmente vengono impiegati protocolli di mono o poli-chemioterapia comprendenti l'utilizzo del cis-platino (DDP) che rappresenta l'agente tumoricida più attivo nell'ovaio. La negatività del second look è sicuramente correlata con la quantità di tumore residuo alla fine dell'intervento chirurgico primario. Le prospettive nel trattamento dei tumori ovarici sono legate all'impiego degli anticorpi monoclonali (CA125), all'impiego di farmaci mielostimolanti (GM-CSF) e alla scoperta di nuovi farmaci attivi nell'ambito di questi tumori.

10. Urogynaecologia International Journal Vol. 5 (2), pag. 81-87. 1991

Pubourethral plication in prolapse surgery.

L. Frigerio, G. Banfi, L. Gandini, A. Pirondini, M. Dindelli, A. Ferrari.

Summary: A long-term clinical follow-up was realized in 103 patients affected by urogenital prolapse with or without "Genuine stress incontinence"(GSI) and treated by "pubourethral plication"(PLPU) during vaginal surgery. "Stress test" was employed for preoperative evaluation of GSI and confronted during long term follow-up. Ninety-two patients (89.3%) had complete postoperative recovery of urogenital prolapse. Pubourethral plication was able to prevent GSI in 96.9% of the patients affected by urogenital prolapse, while the long term follow-up confirmed a cure rate of 74.4% of the cases treated for GSI combined with significative pelvic relaxation ($p < 0.001$).

11. Proceedings of International Gynecologic Cancer Society. Third Biennial Meeting. Cairns, Australia, 22-26 Settembre 1991.

Prognostic factors and survival after radical hysterectomy: actual clinical prospectives

L. Frigerio, L. Busci, A. Pirondini, G. Banfi, A. Ferrari

Summary: In patients affected by cervical cancer at the stages Ib Ila, a reduced 5-yrs survival is related to vascular invasion (35.7%) and lymph node involvement (43.5%) despite large adoption of adjuvant radiotherapy after radical hysterectomy. In more than 1/3 of these patients the sites of failure occurred outside the treatment area. These, then, would give more definitive evidence with regard to the need for systemic adjuvant therapy in high risk patients. More than 1 high risk prognostic factors, but not nodes involvement were present in 18 patients and 5 yrs survival was 77.7% vs. 80.3% in the patients with only 1 high risk factor (n.s.). The opportunity of any adjuvant post-operative treatment is questionable in other subgroups of patients with secondary factors of risk.

12. Italian Journal of Gynecology and Obstetrics Vol 4, 3:109-112, 1992
Cytoplasmic Steroid Receptors in Normal and Neoplastic Endometrial Tissues
L.Frigerio, A.Pirondini, D.Ferrari, L.Busci, E.Rabaiotti, M.Dindelli, A.Ferrari
Summary: Cytosol estradiol and progesterone receptors were evaluated simultaneously normal and neoplastic tissue in 13 cases of endometrial carcinoma. In all patients estrogen receptors demonstrated a greater cytosolic concentration in the tumoral zone than in normal endometrium ($p < 0.001$). Poorly differentiated tumors (G4 according to Broders) had lower Estrogen receptor concentrations in the neoplastic tissue than more differentiated cancers ($p < 0.001$). Peritoneal Washings, lymphnodal evaluation and histologic type were well correlated with progesterone receptor levels in normal uterine tissue ($p < 0.001$).

13. Tumori. 1993 Feb 28;79(1):40-4.

Primary carcinoma of the fallopian tube.

Frigerio L, Pirondini A, Pileri M, Pifarotti G, Busci L, Rabaiotti E, Ferrari A.
IIIa Clinica di Ostetricia e Ginecologia, Università degli Studi di Milano,
Istituto Scientifico S. Raffaele, Italy.

SUMMARY: Twenty-nine patients with fallopian tube cancer were treated at the Gynecologic Oncology Department of Milan University from 1970 to 1988. The mean patient age was 59 years. Parity, symptomatology and histology were considered. Distribution by stage was as follows: I) 11 (37%); II) 10 (34%); III) 8 (27%) according to the Dodson classification. Twenty patients (69%) underwent surgery followed by pelvic irradiation. Adjuvant chemotherapy was performed in the treatment of 5 women with stage 1 disease, 6 with stage 2, and all 8 with stage 3. Five year overall survival was 41.38%: 47.6% at stages 1 and 2, and 25% at stage 3. Radiotherapy has now been replaced by cisplatin-based multiagent chemotherapy. Optimal surgical debulking combined with accurate lymph node sampling are not followed by systematic use of repeat laparotomy. The procedures described in this work improve the clinical assessment and patient survival, and make different series comparable.

BACKGROUND: Because of the rarity of fallopian tube cancer, clinical approaches have changed during the last 18 years.

METHODS: Twenty-nine patients with fallopian tube cancer were treated at the Gynecologic Oncology Department of Milan University from 1970 to 1988. The mean

patient age was 59 years. Parity, symptomatology and histology were considered. Distribution by stage was as follows: I, 11 (37%); II, 10 (34%); III, 8 (27%) according to the Dodson classification. Twenty patients (69%) underwent surgery followed by pelvic irradiation. Adjuvant chemotherapy was performed in the treatment of 5 women with stage I disease, 6 with stage II, and all 8 with stage III.

RESULTS: Five-year overall survival was 41.38%: 47.6% at stages I and II, 25% at stage III. Radiotherapy has not been replaced by cisplatin-based multiagent

chemotherapy. Optimal surgical debulking combined with accurate lymph node sampling are not followed by systematic use of repeat laparotomy.

CONCLUSIONS: The procedures described in this work improve the clinical assessment and patient survival, and make different series comparable.

PMID: 8497921 [PubMed - indexed for MEDLINE]

14. Ann Ostet Ginecol Med Perinat. 1994 115

Luci ed Ombre sul Decorso Post-Operatorio dopo TC oggi.

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SUMMARY: 450 patients submitted to caesarean section in 1993 are evaluated for indications and complications of surgery, maternal pathology and puerperium.

The major indications were for previous cesarean section, maternal illness and fetal distress, while dystocia and fetal sproportion were loss represented.

In our experience little complications because of standardization of surgery, large use of antibiotic and antithrombotic drugs, are related to post-operative hospitalisation with evident advantages for the patient and reduced sanitary costs.